

VOICES OF DISPLACED: A VADER-BASED SENTIMENT ANALYSIS OF AFGHAN REPATRIATES' LONG-TERM LIVED EXPERIENCES IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Afghanistan's protracted displacement crisis has produced millions of long-term refugees in Pakistan, many of whom now face forced repatriation under the government's Illegal Foreigners' Repatriation Plan announced in October 2023. While existing scholarship has examined the geopolitical and legal dimensions of this displacement, the emotional and linguistic experiences of refugees confronting deportation remain underexplored through computational methods. This study addresses this gap by applying VADER-based sentiment analysis in the Orange data mining software to 20 semi-structured interview transcripts from male Afghan refugees aged 50 and above, residing at Chakdara Refugee Camp, District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Interviews were conducted in Pashto from December 2025 to January 2026 and analysed through word clouds, heat maps, box plots, and sentiment distribution curves. The findings reveal coexisting expressions of joy rooted in economic contribution and generational belonging, alongside pervasive fear driven by institutional violence, legal marginalisation, and the threat of return to Taliban-controlled Afghanistan. The study recommends that policymakers incorporate refugee voices and emotional evidence into deliberations on deportation policy.

Keywords: *Afghan Refugees, Forced Repatriation, Orange, Sentiment Analysis, VADER*

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1. Introduction

Afghanistan has remained one of the most enduring sources of forced displacement in modern history. Afghan migration to neighbouring countries, particularly Pakistan, dates to the Soviet invasion of 1979, which triggered the exodus of over three million Afghans seeking refuge across the border (UNHCR, 2023). Subsequent waves of displacement followed the United States-led invasion in 2001 and the Taliban's return to power in August 2021 after the withdrawal of American forces (Hosseini et al., 2024). By October 2023, an estimated 3.8 to 4.4 million Afghan nationals, both documented and undocumented, were residing in Pakistan, many of whom were born and raised there and had never set foot in Afghanistan (Human Rights Watch, 2025). Despite their decades-long presence, these refugees have consistently occupied a precarious legal position, lacking formal citizenship rights and remaining subject to periodic policy shifts that threaten their stability (Alemi et al., 2024).

Figure 1

Afghan refugee families arrive at a transit point near the Pakistan-Afghanistan border. Millions of Afghans have sought refuge in Pakistan since 1979, many of whom have lived there for generations (Source: UNICEF)

In October 2023, the Pakistani caretaker government announced its plan for the Mass Escalation and Mass Repatriation of illegal Foreigners, which is the plan for the illegal deportation of primarily Afghan nationals who do not have valid documentation (Amnesty International, 2024). The first phase had a thirty-day window in which

undocumented Afghans were asked to leave the country voluntarily or face forced removal. More than 468,000 Afghans were returned between October and December 2023 alone (Amnesty International, 2025). Subsequent phases systematically expanded the scope to a group of Afghan Citizen Card holders, and possibly to Proof of Registration card holders registered with UNHCR. International human rights organisations, such as Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch, have criminalised deportations as a breach of the principle of non-refoulement, as it is feared that returnees may face persecution, extrajudicial killings, and massive restrictions on the exercise of fundamental freedoms under the Taliban's rule (Human Rights Watch, 2025). The policy has been accompanied by reports of night-time raids, arbitrary detention, confiscation of property, and destruction of identity documents (Amnesty International, 2025).

Figure 2

Afghan families gather with their belongings at a border crossing point during Pakistan's mass repatriation drive, 2023. Over 468,000 Afghans were returned between October and December 2023 alone (Source: Reuters).

While a large amount of scholastic work has been devoted to the geopolitical and legal aspects of Afghan displacement, relatively few works have focused on the emotional and psychological experiences of long-term refugees faced with forced repatriation through their own linguistic expression. Kantor et al. (2023) pointed out that Afghan refugees are faced with complex post-migration challenges that include mental health

issues and interpersonal stress factors, along with institutional barriers that are not easily captured by standard clinical instrumentation. Similarly, studies among Afghan refugee populations have continually shown that pre-migration trauma and post-migration stressors interact in ways that will result in a deep psychological distress, with elements such as legal precariousness, economic marginalisation, and cultural dislocation stacking the decks against the trauma of displacement (Aleml et al., 2024). However, there is still a significant lack of application of computational linguistic methods to analyse the sentiments and emotions embedded in refugees' first-person narratives.

Sentiment analysis, a subset of natural language processing (NLP), provides a methodical means of determining and measuring emotional orientations in textual data. The VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner) tool has been developed by Hutto and Gilbert (2014). It is a lexicon- and rule-based model that has been well validated for its ability to detect sentiment polarity and intensity across various types of text. VADER produces positive, negative, neutral, and compound sentiment scores, allowing researchers to chart the emotional landscape of a given corpus with reasonable precision (Hutto & Gilbert, 2014). Recent studies have successfully used VADER and similar NLP tools to analyse public discourse on migration, examining how sentiment patterns change in response to policy events and media framing (Wildemann et al., 2023; Rabi & Rabi, 2025).

This research uses VADER-based sentiment analysis in the context of the Orange software environment to discuss the lived experiences of twenty long-term Afghan refugees in Pakistan facing repatriation under the government's policy of deportation. By analysing the interview transcripts, the research identifies dominant patterns of positive and negative sentiments, recurring emotional themes, and the linguistic strategies by which the refugees articulate their identities, fears, and attachments. The study makes a significant contribution to the growing intersection of computational linguistics and the study of forced migration by foregrounding the voices of people in forced migration, using a data-driven analytical framework. In doing so, it responds to the call by Gokani et al. (2023) and others for research methodologies that place the subjective experiences of displaced populations at the centre rather than reducing them to statistical categories. The findings have implications for policymakers, humanitarian organisations, and researchers who are keen to understand the human cost of mass deportation policies in the South Asian context.

2. Literature Review

The scholarly discourse surrounding Afghan refugees in Pakistan spans multiple disciplines, encompassing forced migration studies, legal analysis, psychological research, media framing, and, more recently, computational linguistics. This section reviews the existing literature across these intersecting domains to contextualise the present study's use

of VADER-based sentiment analysis for examining the lived experiences of long-term Afghan refugees facing repatriation.

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2.1. Sentiment Analysis, Computational Tools, and Emotion Theory in Migration Research

Afghanistan has given birth to one of the longest refugee crises in modern history. Siddikoglu and Sagiroglu (2023) traced the roots of Afghan displacement to the invasion of Afghanistan by the Soviet Union in 1979, and that Pakistan's initial open-door policy gradually became ad-hoc and progressively restrictive as the displacement became protracted. By the early 2020s, the number of people who were Afghan refugees living in Pakistan had risen to between three and four million, making it one of the largest refugee hosting countries in the world.

Mielke and Etzold (2022) used the lens of figurational approach to explore the shrinking mobility ladder for the Afghans in Pakistan, arguing that the lack of national refugee law, along with socio-economic precarity and an everyday protection limbo, provided a structural environment in which younger Afghans were torn between their desire to belong and the nauseating forces of institutional marginalisation. Their qualitative findings showed that the many Afghans experienced their presence in Pakistan, not as protracted displacement in the first place, but more as a temporary and agentic migration, which was eroded over time by compressing legal and structural pressures.

The issue of identity and belonging of Afghan refugees in Pakistan has been the focus of considerable scholarly attention. Iqbal et al (2025), have completed a sociological study about lived experiences of involuntary migration amongst Afghan immigrants in Peshawar and the findings indicate that refugees performed complex intersections of social exclusion, economic marginalisation and cultural negotiation as part of their host communities, employing various coping strategies at individual, family and communities levels in order to preserve their social cohesion despite barriers in the systems. Their mixed methods research uncovered difficult legal and administrative obstacles, economic disparities and complex dynamics of social integration experienced by Afghan immigrants. These findings are consistent with the current study's finding that references to burial sites, generational settlement, and economic contribution are among the themes refugees use to describe their attachment to Pakistan, and figure prominently in the sentiment analysis of the interview data.

The legal and institutional aspects of the experience of Afghan refugees in Pakistan have been critically analyzed by several scholars. Amnesty International (2024) reported on the violation of the principle of non-refoulement in the context of Pakistan's case that involved the forced return of refugees to a country (Pakistan in this case) where they would encounter persecution under the Taliban regime. Human Rights Watch (2025) reported that the campaign of deportation was accompanied by night raiding, arbitrariness of

detention, property confiscation, and the destruction of identity documents, effectively leaving refugees without the status of a legal person.

Khan et al. (2024) examined the barriers experienced by undocumented Afghan immigrants in Peshawar in terms of access to healthcare, education, livelihood, and human rights protections and found that, consequently, the systemic exclusion from social services was compounded by psychological distress associated with the displaced life. These institutional vulnerabilities are evidenced by the negative sentiment patterns found in this current study, where the participants use language associated with fear, humiliation, and structural oppression.

The psychological and emotional cost of forced displacement to the people of Afghanistan has been well documented. Kantor et al (2023) conducted a multi-method study on the Afghan asylum seekers and refugees and identified six major themes of self-perceived problems, which included post-migration living difficulties, general mental health problems, interpersonal stressors, and institutional barriers. Their findings reinforced the importance of standardised clinical measures failing to capture the subjective intensity of problems experienced by refugees and underscored the value of qualitative and linguistic approaches.

Hosseini et al. (2024) found a systematic review of evidence-based mental health interventions among Afghan refugees in which they emphasized how the pre-displacement stressors, the post-migration challenges, and the discouple discourse between the Afghans and their host has compounded psychological problematic. The role of media in the public perceptions of Afghan refugees has been analysed using the concept of peace journalism. Jehangir (2023) conducted a critical discourse analysis of Pakistani English-language media coverage of Afghan refugees and their forced repatriation, finding that conflict-escalatory frames were the dominant framing and that the media stance shifted over time to reflect state policy. Her research showed that stereotypical narratives of Afghan refugees as threats and burdens had become the order of the day in daily reporting and helped to legitimise the dehumanisation and forced removal of refugees. This media framing becomes an important backdrop in which the sentiments expressed by refugees in the present study must be understood, for institutional and public discourse directly shape the conditions of fear, exclusion and vulnerability that permeate the narratives of participants.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

This study adopts a qualitative research design grounded in an interpretivist paradigm, seeking to explore the lived experiences, emotions, and identity constructions of long-term Afghan refugees in Pakistan who face forced repatriation under the government's Illegal Foreigners' Repatriation Plan. The research employs semi-structured

interviews as its primary data collection instrument, complemented by VADER-based sentiment analysis conducted in Orange data mining software to systematically examine the interview corpus for emotional and thematic patterns. This mixed-methods integration of qualitative interviewing and computational text analysis enables the study to capture both the depth of individual refugee narratives and the broader patterns of sentiment pervading the dataset.

3.2. Participants and Sampling

The study employed purposive sampling to recruit 20 male Afghan refugees aged 50 years and above, all of whom had resided in Pakistan for at least 27 years. All participants were residing at or near the Chakdara Refugee Camp, District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province, Pakistan. The age criterion ensured that participants possessed extensive first-hand experience of displacement, settlement, and the evolving policy landscape governing Afghan refugees in Pakistan. The prolonged residency requirement guaranteed that participants could speak to the deep generational, economic, and emotional ties that long-term displacement produces. The following table presents the demographic profile of the participants.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Participants

#	Name	Age	Origin	Years in PK	Occupation
1	Shafoor Khan	62	Nangarhar, Afghanistan	38	Cloth merchant
2	Baseer Ahmad	58	Kunar, Afghanistan	35	Retired schoolteacher
3	Shafiqullah	55	Paktia, Afghanistan	33	Auto mechanic
4	Noor Ullah	67	Logar, Afghanistan	42	Fruit seller (retired)
5	Zakir Ullah	52	Khost, Afghanistan	30	Construction contractor
6	Ghulam Muhammad	71	Wardak, Afghanistan	43	Retired labourer / Elder
7	Abdul Wali Khan	54	Bajaur (originally Kunar)	31	Timber and furniture business
8	Azizullah	59	Laghman, Afghanistan	36	Shopkeeper (general store)
9	Sheren Zada	63	Baghlan, Afghanistan	40	Carpet weaver and trader

10	Tariq Shah	50	Ghazni, Afghanistan	28	Restaurant owner
11	Afzali Khan	56	Helmand, Afghanistan	34	Truck driver
12	Khan Zada	61	Zabul, Afghanistan	37	Livestock trader
13	Abdullah Shah	53	Kunduz, Afghanistan	29	Tailor / Garment worker
14	Rustam Khan	65	Panjshir, Afghanistan	39	Gemstone trader
15	Bakhshullah	57	Takhar, Afghanistan	32	Baker (naan shop)
16	Zareen Khan	60	Nangarhar, Afghanistan	36	Money exchange dealer
17	Shahabuddin	55	Parwan, Afghanistan	33	Pharmacy owner
18	Gul Amin	68	Badakhshan, Afghanistan	41	Retired construction worker / Elder
19	Wakeel Khan	51	Maidan Wardak, Afghanistan	27	Scrap metal dealer
20	Group Discussion	50–71	Multiple	27–43	Various

Note: Interview 20 was a group discussion at Chakdara Refugee Camp, Dir

Lower.

3.3. Data Collection

Data were collected from 15 December 2025 to 31 January 2026. All 20 interviews were conducted in Pashto only, to ensure linguistic comfort and authenticity of expression. Interviews were then transcribed verbatim and translated into English by the researchers. The translation was validated by two prominent linguists specialized in translation studies. The semi-structured interview guide explored eight thematic domains, including migration history and the establishment in Pakistan, emotional and psychological impact of the repatriation order, sense of belonging, home and identity, economic consequences, family and educational disruption, burial and spiritual ties to Pakistani soil, gratitude, indebtedness and the betrayal and fears of returning to Taliban controlled Afghanistan. Informed consent was obtained from all the participants before the interviews. It must be noted that participants' real names are used with their explicit permission, as interview

participants wanted to be identified by name to reclaim their visibility and dignity from institutional erasure.

3.4. Data Analysis

The transcribed and translated interview data were analysed using computational sentiment analysis in the Orange data mining software (Demšar et al., 2013). The VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner) is a sentiment analysis tool (Hutto & Gilbert, 2014), which is embedded as an add-on to the text mining tool Orange, and was used on the corpus of 20 interview transcripts to produce four sentiment scores for each response, namely positive, negative, neutral, and compound. The compound score, ranging from -1 (most negative) to +1 (most positive), was used as the overall indicator of the emotional orientation in each transcript. The sentiment data was then visualised using several Orange features.

A *Word Cloud* was created to identify the keywords that appear most frequently across the corpus and to find dominant lexical patterns relating to identity, displacement and emotional attachment. A *Heatmap* was used to display the strength of emotional expression across all 20 interviews using colour gradients. A *Box Plot* was used to identify emotional divergence across the dataset, based on Paul Ekman's (1992) classification of basic emotions, to identify the dominant emotional markers of fear and joy in the corpus. Additionally, *Distribution Curves* were created separately for positive and negative sentiments to analyze the distribution of emotional polarity over the entire dataset. This multi-layered approach to analysis allowed these researchers to go beyond the surface-level of reading them thematically and to systematically examine the emotional architecture that went into the volunteers' first-person narratives.

3.5. Results and Discussion

This section presents VADER-based sentiment analysis findings from 20 interview transcripts of long-term Afghan refugees at Chakdara Refugee Camp, Pakistan, which were analyzed using Orange data mining software. The results are visualised through sentiment scores, *Word Clouds*, *Heatmaps*, *Box Plots*, and *Distribution Curves*.

Title	Document	positive	negative	neutral	compound
Interview 1: Abdul Wa...	Textonly00_H...	0.041	0.203	0.752	-0.913
Interview 2: Collo...	Textonly00_...	0.045	0.129	0.822	-0.903
Interview 3: Sher Za...	Textonly00_...	0.047	0.143	0.804	-0.902
Interview 4: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.048	0.148	0.793	-0.899
Interview 5: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.025	0.091	0.881	-0.929
Interview 6: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.051	0.124	0.824	-0.914
Interview 7: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.051	0.136	0.813	-0.912
Interview 8: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.073	0.174	0.753	-0.918
Interview 9: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.08	0.124	0.795	-0.914
Interview 10: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.029	0.084	0.887	-0.921
Interview 11: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.024	0.1	0.877	-0.925
Interview 12: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.031	0.07	0.877	-0.948
Interview 13: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.081	0.152	0.765	-0.918
Interview 14: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.075	0.1	0.824	-0.899
Interview 15: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.077	0.05	0.872	-0.912
Interview 16: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.084	0.084	0.831	-0.948
Interview 17: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.09	0.091	0.819	-0.918
Interview 18: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.086	0.097	0.817	-0.912
Interview 19: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.087	0.072	0.84	-0.942
Interview 20: Shahid E...	Textonly00_...	0.091	0.07	0.84	-0.948

Figure 3
Data table of Sentiment Scores

Figure 3 shows the overall responses of the participants in the data table generated in Orange using the VADER filter to identify dominant sentiments, including positive, negative, neutral, and compound in the created dataset. This dataset comprises 20 interviews that were on the lived experiences of long-term Afghan refugees in Pakistan facing repatriation under Pakistan’s deportation policy. Following a detailed analysis of participants' responses, the researchers identified that the highest positive sentiment score in the dataset was 0.096, while the lowest was 0.017. While the highest negative sentiment was 0.203, the lowest was 0.047. The highest neutral sentiment value in the corpus was 0.933, and the lowest was 0.572. Additionally, the highest compound sentiment value was 0.9508, while the lowest was -0.9976.

Figure 4**3.6. Word Cloud of the Most Frequently Occurring Keyword**

The *Word Cloud* feature visualises the most frequently occurring words in the dataset. The most common keywords include: I (281), my (87), year (64), Pakistan (59), Afghan (55), Pakistani (54), us (52), that (45), what (44), we (42), he (34), family (30), country (29). The participants have frequently used words such as Pakistan, country, and Afghan to express their national and social identities in their host country, Pakistan. The word *back* indicates their forced deportation and their belonging to their country of origin. 'Home' demonstrates the redefinition of refugees' home, as for years they were living in Pakistan, their dead are buried, their children are born, and their memories are made in Pakistan.

However, the frequent use of the word *Taliban* indicates fear of return, as many people mention their fear of returning to a country occupied by the Islamic extremist forces, who do not allow any freedom, especially for refugees returning, and are more concerned about the education of their female children in Afghanistan. The word *Children* talks about the kids that are born in Pakistan and are not growing. Their parents seem more worried about their education and future in Afghanistan, and this deportation will put a question mark on their future. Overall, the analysis of the linguistic choices in the word cloud reveals that most of these words reflect individual and collective identity, as well as experiences and emotions after being asked to return to Pakistan after living there for so many years.

Figure 5

3.7. Heatmap of the Sentiments

The sentiment scores positive, negative, neutral, and compound are further visualised through the Heat Map feature of the software to illustrate further the intensity of emotions using colour coding, where dense colours indicate higher emotional intensity. In comparison, lighter colours represent lower intensity across the data. In the figure, emotions are visualised using three distinct colours: blue represents negative emotions, magenta indicates less intense emotions, and yellow signifies the least negative or most positive emotions. Each response in Figure 3 is colored according to the intensity of emotion conveyed in its content.

Figure 6

3.8. Box Plot of Emotions

The box plot feature in the Orange software reveals emotional divergence and clear distinctions among emotional states, as described by Ekman (1992). In the figure above, the software has identified only two emotion types in the compiled dataset. Of all the uploaded interview data, only one interview shows traces of fear, an emotional marker, while the rest show comparatively high levels of joy. In interview 12, the central theme that appears is fear. The words like ‘terrified’, ‘humiliation’, ‘drag people out’, ‘crying’, ‘killed’, ‘bomb’, ‘dangerous’, ‘exile’, and suspicion create a discourse filled with anxiety with institutional vulnerability. The report is structured by scenes of night arrests, forced deportation, death, and ongoing uncertainty. The emotion of fear has been depicted in multiple ways: Fear of violence and bombings, fear of imprisonment and deportation, and

fear of survival and belonging. The participant stated, “We are the face of that fear,” reflecting how people experience fear in their daily lives about migration and returning to their country of origin. On the other hand, data from other interviews show comparatively positive emotional expressions, such as gratitude, a sense of contribution, strength, pride, and emotional attachment to people and place. Words such as "business," "work," "education," "children," "belonging," and "years of life" reflect a desire to stay permanently. In these interviews, joy is not obvious directly. They are not observable to the naked eye, but software can detect them quite efficiently. Some of the example responses are “feeling proud of earning money” or “helping Pakistan’s economy”, “a deep connection with the graves of their loved ones” and “feeling thankful to the common people living around” them in Pakistan.

3.9. Dominant Themes in the Corpus

3.9.1. Positive Themes in the Corpus

Figure 7

3.10. Positive Sentiments Distribution Curve across the Corpus

3.10.1. Afghan Financial Contribution to Pakistan

The central, recurring positive pattern throughout the dataset is the claim that refugees contribute financially. They consistently portray themselves not as dependent but as nation builders, merchants, workers, and supporters of Pakistan's economy. This demonstrates dignity, self-worth, and social inclusion. Words like ‘build houses’, ‘commercial spaces’, ‘businesses’, ‘livestock commerce’, ‘economic input’, ‘employment’, and ‘strengthen this discourse. This optimistic perspective emerges not from comfort, but from self-esteem and economic output. For instance, as the respondents stated, “The Afghan livestock trade is the backbone of meat markets in Dir and beyond.” Indicates that Afghan merchants are key players in the market. The metaphor ‘backbone’ suggests core institutional importance. Another example is “Without us, the price of meat

would skyrocket”, which demonstrates the state discourse of forced immigrants as a financial burden on Pakistan. It reconstructs as an economic stabiliser of the local commercial system. “These hand-built houses here” show hard work and belonging to their profession. It links the refugees' financial input to a sentimental bond with their efforts. “We have worked here for thirty-seven years” indicates that long-term presence enhances the social acceptance of input. Labour serves as evidence of social acceptance. Additionally, “We contribute more than we take” shows the open resistance to institutional framing. It demonstrates awareness of public charges and addresses the issue with an economic contribution argument, as if they were not living here for free.

3.11. The Sentimental Belonging and Generational Lineage in Pakistan

Another prominent positive pattern is emotional connection to the host country. Refugees express the connection through the graves of their loved ones, children, memories, and the years they were living here. “Home” is reframed not by citizenship but by the experience of living in Pakistan. This recurring pattern is obvious through these words: Burial sites, Children born in Pakistan, generational patterns of settlement, and social integration. This reveals happiness in emotional attachment to the host country and its people, even amid instability. For instance, “My wife is buried here”, “My children were born here,” “Home is where you bury your dead”, which demonstrates that their loved ones are buried here, which shows emotional attachment to this place. Some respondents stated that their children were born here. Birth creates lineal roots. Moreover, “We grew old here” indicates ageing in a single setting, implying a lifetime dedication and a time-based attachment. Moreover, “Thirty-seven temporary years.” Although contradictory, this statement reveals an intense emotional connection despite juridical insecurity.

3.12. Negative Themes in the Corpus

Figure 8

3.13. Negative Sentiments Distribution Curve across the Corpus

3.13.1. Fear, Insecurity, and Violence of the Institution

Fear is prominently evident in the corpus, especially in the twelfth interview. It surfaces in portrayals of official operations, Taliban bloodshed, explosions, and exile threats. Fear runs at three levels in the Corpus: Physical fear of violence and bombings, structural fear like police raids and documentation, and existential fear, for example, deportation from the country. For instance, “With fear. Pure fear” conveys clear sentimental identification and undeniable nervousness. “They come at night, banging on doors,” shows that night raids create mental panic and insecurity. “A roadside bomb killed him,” demonstrates a personal loss linked to exile to deadly risk. “We are being treated like criminals”, suggests that marginalisation creates societal fear and degradation. Moreover, “Pakistan to Afghanistan is not ‘going home.’ It is the first step of another journey of displacement,” indicates removal from the country is constructed as repeated expulsion, not protection.

3.14. Legal Marginalisation and Institutional Bias against Refugees

The recurring negative pattern is structural marginalisation. Forced immigrants portray official degradation, no ownership rights, and a lasting short-term status. This suggests institutional oppression rather than individual-level aggression. For example, “I cannot buy property in my name” indicates that the respondent is unable to purchase property, thereby limiting their lasting belonging to the host country. “I cannot open a bank account easily,” demonstrates economic marginalisation, which hinders financial advancement. “Every renewal is a humiliation”, “For thirty-seven years, I have been ‘temporary.’” It suggests that the refugee’s documentation process creates recurring mental humiliation and time-related contradiction. Moreover, “We are a political tool” demonstrates the perception of exploitation by institutional figures.

4. Conclusion

This research used VADER-based sentiment analysis in the Orange data mining environment to analyze the emotional and linguistic aspects of the lived experiences of twenty long-term Afghan refugees in Pakistan under the threat of forced repatriation. The findings reveal a complex emotional picture in which joy and fear are closely juxtaposed in the corpus. Positive sentiments were coming not out of comfort but out of deeply embedded claims of economic contribution, generational belonging, and emotional attachment to Pakistani soil via burial sites, children born in the country, and decades of labour. Conversely, negative sentiments were focused on institutional fear, legal marginalisation, structural humiliation, and the existential fear of being sent back to Taliban-controlled Afghanistan. The dominance of neutral sentiment scores over most of the interviews signifies that the language used by refugees in narrating their experiences is characterised by temperate and measured expressions of suffering, rather than explicit and emotional language, a measurement that highlights the importance of using computational tools in detecting emotional undercurrents that are surfaced and overlooked

by surface-level reading. The study shows that combining sentiment analysis with qualitative migration research is a useful methodological contribution that can help researchers to systematically map the emotional structure of narratives of displaced populations. These findings have direct implications for policymakers, demanding a rethink of mass deportation policies that show no regard for deep, human bonds formed over decades of settlement, and for humanitarian organisations seeking evidence-based strategies to increase refugee voices in advocacy and intervention design.

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